

Studies on Some Isomeric *bis*-2-Thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos

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Preparation and properties including $\lambda_{\max}$ values, of *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos containing a chlorine atom at positions 4:4' and 6:6', bromine atom at positions 4:4', 6:6' and 7:7', iodine atom at positions 4:4', 5:5', 6:6', 7:7' and methoxy group at positions 5:5', 6:6' and 7:7' have been recorded. The $\lambda_{\max}$ values of previously known *bis*-2-(5-chloro), *bis*-2-(7-chloro) and *bis*-2-(5-bromo) dyes have been measured. The different series of dyes have been arranged on the basis of the absorption data. A possible reason, for absorption at lower wave lengths of these ethylene-indigos, compared to the corresponding thioindigoids has been offered.

In this communication we describe the preparation of a series of dyestuffs of the type I (a-1). Literature connected with these *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethylene indigos is quite meagre and except in one case no systematic study of this class has been undertaken. Thus Dutt¹ has described the preparation of three naphthothionaphthene-ethylene-indigos, while Guha and Chatterjee² have reported the preparation of *bis*-2-(5-chloro-, 7-chloro-, and 5-bromo)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigos. These authors, however, have not measured the $\lambda_{\max}$ values of the dyes. Earlier Guha³ had reported the preparation of *bis*-2-(4-, 5-, 6- and 7-methyl)thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos and on the basis of the $\lambda_{\max}$ values showed the gradation to be: 5-methyl dye > unsubstituted dye > 4-methyl dye > 6-methyl dye > 7-methyl dye.

In the present work the preparation and properties of *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos of the type (I) have been undertaken, in order to study the effect of a chlorine, a bromine or an iodine atom or a methoxy group on colour when present in the different positions of *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo.

I(a-1)

I _a	R=4:4'-Chloro;	I _h	=6:6'-Iodo
I _b	R=6:6'-Chloro;	I _i	=7:7'-Iodo
I _c	R=4:4'-Bromo;	I _j	=5:5'-Methoxy
I _d	R=6:6'-Bromo;	I _k	=6:6'-Methoxy
I _e	R=7:7'-Bromo;	I _l	=7:7'-Methoxy
I _f	R=4:4'-Iodo;		
I _g	R=5:5'-Iodo		

The dyes I_{a-l} were obtained in 60-78% yield by condensing glyoxal sodium bisulphite with the appropriate thioindoxyl⁴⁻¹⁵ (*vide* Experimental) and possess violet-red, deep-red and violet shades. They are soluble in xylene, nitrobenzene and pyridine but are very little soluble in ethanol, methanol, ether, etc. The dyes did not melt up to 360°. They gave the correct C-H analysis results, and the $\lambda_{\max}$ values and other details are recorded in Table I. The $\lambda_{\max}$ values of the three dyes namely *bis*-2-(5-chloro)-, *bis*-2-(7-chloro)- and *bis*-2-(5-bromo)thionaphthene ethyleneindigos have been recorded and they are 535 nm, 525 nm and 540 nm respectively. It is now, therefore, possible to arrange the 4-isomeric *bis*-2-(4-, 5-, 6- and 7-chloro) thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos on the basis of their decreasing $\lambda_{\max}$ values as shown below:

5-chloro dye > 4-chloro dye > 7-chloro dye > 6-chloro dye. The order of gradation with the isomeric bromo and iodo dyes, is also the same. The three isomeric methoxy dyes may similarly be arranged as under:

5-Methoxy dye > 7-methoxy dye > 6-methoxy dye.

Since the unsubstituted dye absorbs maximally at 483.5 nm, it may be concluded that in these *bis*-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos, either chloro, bromo, iodo or methoxy substituents invariably produce a bathochromic shift. The $\lambda_{\max}$ data of the *bis*-2-thionaphthene-indigos (collected from the literature) are given in Table 2 for ready reference. A comparison of these data with the values for the corresponding *bis*-ethyleneindigos reveal that not withstanding the extension of conjugation in the ethyleneindigos a hypsochromic effect is invariably produced, indicating that in the molecules of these

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Name of the dye	Name of the component reacting with G	Colour ; Solvent of cristo	% Yield (crude)	λ_{max} in nm	
1	2	3	4	5		
1.	bis-2-(4-Chloro) TEI	4-Chloro Th	+	Violet-red Xylene	68	528
2.	bis-2-(6-Chloro) TEI	6-Chloro Th	+	Deep red-violet Xylene	60	520
3.	bis-2-(4-Bromo) TEI	4-Bromo Th	+	Violet-red Pyridine	62	532
4.	bis-2-(6-Bromo) TEI	6-Bromo Th	+	Violet-red Pyridine	70	515
5.	bis-2-(7-Bromo) TEI	7-Bromo Th	+	Violet-red Pyridine	70	528
6.	bis-2-(4-Iodo)-TEI	4-Iodo Th	+	Chocolate-red Xylene	78	504
7.	bis-2-(5-Iodo)-TEI	5-Iodo Th	+	Violet-red Xylene	74	510
8.	bis-2-(6-Iodo)-TEI	6-Iodo Th	+	Violet-red Xylene	74	500
9.	bis-2-(7-Iodo)-TEI	7-Iodo Th	+	Red-violet Xylene	74	502
10.	bis-2-(5-Methoxy)-TEI	5-Methoxy Th	+	Deep red-violet Xylene	65	528
11.	bis-2-(6-Methoxy)-TEI	6-Methoxy Th	+	Deep red-violet Xylene	62	516
12.	bis-2-(7-Methoxy)-TEI	7-Methoxy Th	+	Deep red-violet Xylene	62	522

TEI—THIONAPHTHENE-ETHYLENEINDIGO ; G=GLYOXAL SODIUM BISULPHITE ; Th—THIOINDOXYL

dyes some degree of steric inhibition of resonance occurs and so in all probability they have the cisoid structure II (cf. isoindigo and indigo).

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Name of dye	λ_{max} in nm and Ref. No.
1.	4 : 4'-Dichloro T*	— 550 16
2.	5 : 5'-Dichloro T	— 559 16
3.	6 : 6'-Dichloro T	— 538 16
4.	7 : 7'-Dichloro T	— 545 16
5.	4 : 4'-Dibromo T	— 549 17
6.	5 : 5'-Dibromo T	— 562 9
7.	6 : 6'-Dibromo T	— 547 18
8.	7 : 7'-Dibromo T	— 548 18
9.	4 : 4'-Diiodo T	— 552 19
10.	5 : 5'-Diiodo T	— 566 19
11.	6 : 6'-Diiodo T	— 543 19
12.	7 : 7'-Diiodo T	— 550 19
13.	5 : 5'-Dimethoxy T	— 588 20
14.	6 : 6'-Dimethoxy T	— 474 20
15.	7 : 7'-Dimethoxy T	— 574 20

* T=Thioindigo.

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Experimental

bis-2-Thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos :

These dyes were obtained by condensing 1 mole of glyoxal sodium bisulphite with 2 moles of corresponding thioindoxyls in refluxing ethanolic solution in presence of catalytic amount of conc. HCl. The condensations occurred smoothly and the dyes were obtained in 60-78% yield. The crude dyes were filtered, washed and recrystallised from suitable solvents.